

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/351528812>

A COMPREHENSIVE SYNOPSIS OF THE CURRENT PRACTICE PAVEMENT STRUCTURE DESIGN METHOD OF LIBERIA AND THE NEED FOR AN IMPROVEMENT

Article · May 2021

CITATIONS

0

READS

1,293

1 author:

[Nuushuun Archie Gboe](#)

Vilnius Gediminas Technical University

2 PUBLICATIONS 0 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Liberia Pavement Design [View project](#)

Mechanistic-Empirical Asphalt Pavement Structure Design [View project](#)

A COMPREHENSIVE SYNOPSIS OF THE CURRENT PRACTICE PAVEMENT STRUCTURE DESIGN METHOD OF LIBERIA AND THE NEED FOR AN IMPROVEMENT.

By Nuushuun Archie Gboe

Master Candidate, Innovative Road and Bridge Engineering

Vilnius Gediminas Technical University (joint master with Riga Technical University)

Abstract. Pavement design is an important fragment in the design and construction of roads. The pavement provides a smooth riding surface for vehicular traffic. The current pavement structure design method used in Liberia is the 1993 American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) Guide for Pavement Structure Design which is based on an empirical interpretation of results from the 1960 AASHTO Road Test. The aim of this paper is to summarize the limitation of the 1993 AASHTO Guide for Pavement Structure Design and discussed why the method does not suit Liberia and point out the defect roads in Liberia are experiencing due to the limitation of the current pavement design method used. Finally, I recommend the need for Liberia to develop its Guidelines for Geometric and Pavement Design and effectively and efficiently transition to the Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Design method; and introduce an infrastructure management system.

Keywords: pavement design, pavement performance, 1993 AASHTO Guide for Pavement Structure Design

Introduction

Pavement provides a smooth surface over which vehicles may safely pass under all climatic conditions for the specific performance period of the pavement (*Chapter 1 - NHI-05-037 - Geotech - Bridges & Structures - Federal Highway Administration*, n.d.). Pavement consists of superimposed layers of processed materials above the natural soil sub-grade, whose primary function is to distribute the applied vehicle load to the subgrade. The pavement structure provides a surface of acceptable riding quality, adequate skid resistance, favorable light reflecting characteristics, and low noise pollution. The pavement structure ensures that the transmitted stresses due to wheel load are sufficiently reduced not to exceed the bearing capacity of the sub-grade (O’Flaherty, 2020).

Pavement design aims to select the most economical pavement thickness and composition, which provide a satisfactory level of service for the anticipated traffic; to

achieve this goal, the designer must have sufficient knowledge of the materials, the traffic, the local environment -and their interaction – to be able to predict the performance of any pavement composition (Austroads, 2017). Furthermore, the pavement design engineers must have adequate knowledge of what level of performance, pavement condition, and circumstances are associated with the designed pavement structure.

1. Pavement structures based on the structural performance

Pavement structures are classified based on the structural performance into two, flexible pavement and rigid pavement.

Flexible pavement generally consists of an asphalt-bound surface course or layer on top of the unbound base and subbase granular layers over the subgrade soil. Hot mix asphalt concrete produced by an asphalt plant is the most common surface layer material for flexible pavements, especially for moderately

to heavily trafficked highways. Dense-grade (i.e., well-graded with a low void ratio) aggregates with a maximum aggregate size of about 25mm (1 in.) are most commonly used in hot mix asphalt concrete. However, a wide variety of other types of gradations (e. g., gap-graded) have also been used successfully for specialized conditions (*Chapter 1 - NHI-05-037 - Geotech - Bridges & Structures - Federal Highway Administration, n.d.*).

1.1. Flexible pavements

Flexible pavements will transmit wheel load stresses to the lower layers by grain-to-grain transfer through the point of contact in the granular structure.

Figure 1. Load transfer in granular structure ((O’Flaherty, 2020)

Figure 1 shows that the wheel load acting on the pavement is distributed to a wider area, and the stress decreases with the depth. Given the advantage of this stress distribution characteristic, the flexible pavement normally has many layers typically. Hence, the design of flexible pavement uses the concept of a layered system. Based on this, the flexible pavement may be constructed in

several layers and the top layers have to be of quality to sustain maximum comprehensive stress, also, to wear and tear (O’Flaherty, 2020).

Flexible pavements are constructed using bituminous materials. These can be either in form of the surface treatment (such as bituminous surface treatments generally found on low-volume roads) or asphalt concrete surface courses (generally used on high-volume roads such as national highways) (O’Flaherty, 2020).

1.2. Rigid pavement

Rigid pavement generally consists of Portland cement pavement slabs constructed on a granular base layer over the subgrade soil. The base layer serves to increase the effective stiffness of the slab foundation. The base layer also provides the additional function, plus the base must also prevent pumping of fine-grained soils at joints, cracks, and edges of the slab. Gradation characteristics of the base and subbase are critical here. They may also be stabilized with asphalt or cement to improve their ability to perform this function. A subbase layer is occasionally included between the base layer and the subgrade (*Chapter 1 - NHI-05-037 - Geotech - Bridges & Structures - Federal Highway Administration, n.d.*).

Rigid pavements have sufficient flexural strength to transmit the wheel load stresses to a wider area below. A typical cross-section of the rigid pavement is shown in Figure 2. Compared to the flexible pavement, rigid pavement is placed directly on the prepared sub-grade or a single layer of granular or stabilized material. Since there is only one layer of material between the concrete and the sub-grade, this layer can be called a base or sub-base course (O’Flaherty, 2020).

Figure 2. Typical cross-section of a rigid pavement (O’Flaherty, 2020)

In rigid pavement, the load is distributed by the slab action, and the pavement behaves like an elastic plate resting on a viscous medium (Figure 2). Rigid pavement is constructed by Portland cement concrete (PCC) and should be analyzed by plate theory instead of layer theory, assuming an elastic plate resting on a viscous foundation.

Traditionally fatigue cracking has been considered as the Principal or only criterion for rigid pavement design. The allowable number of load repetitions that cause fatigue cracking depends on the stress ratio between flexural tensile stress and concrete modulus of rupture. Of late, pumping is identified as an essential failure criterion. Pumping is the ejection of soil slurry through the joints and cracks of cement concrete pavement, caused during the downward movement of the slab under the heavy wheel loads. Other significant types of distress in rigid pavement include faulting, spalling, and deterioration.

2. Pavement Structure Design Method and practice of Liberia

Up to date, Liberia is yet to develop its design standards and guideline for pavement structure, geometric design (Agency, 2013); Liberia has a road network with a total length of 10,600 km. Of these, only 657 km are paved while 9,943 km are unpaved and the paved road experience significant deterioration due to design fault, overloading,

and environmental effect. Most projects funded by the government are often designed by consulting companies or contractors as a design-build contract, not by the ministry of public works, which is the infrastructure arm of the government.

Pavement designs are performed using the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AAHSTO) Guide for Pavement Structure Design 1993.

AASHTO 1993 Guide for Design of Pavement Structure is based on empirical models drawn from field performance data measured at the AASHO Road Test in the late 1950s located just northwest of Ottawa, Illinois, about 80 mile south-west of Chicago, along with some theoretical support for layer coefficients and drainage factors (Board, 1962). The AASHTO 1993 Guide for Design of Pavement Structure is based on an empirical approach. The design input parameters/ data, including loads, materials, layers configurations, and environmental conditions, and the pavement structure, were obtained through field/ engineering experience, experimental observations, or blending of both.

The overall serviceability of the pavement is quantified by the Present Serviceability Index (PSI), a complete performance measure combining cracking, patching, rutting, and other distress. Roughness is the dominant factor governing PSI and is, therefore, the principal component of the pavement performance measure. The AAHSTO Guide for Design of Pavement Structure for many years serves as the primary document used to design new and rehabilitated highway pavement and have served the industry well, but have deficiencies due to some of the limitation of the AASHO Road Test (Li et al., 2011).

2.1. Limitation of the Pavement Structure Design Method used in Liberia

The American Association of State Highway Officials (AASHTO) Road Test was a breakthrough for engineers to comprehend how pavement operate but have some limitation due to the nature of the AASHTO Road Test, key among those limitations is.

2.1.1. Performance criteria

The serviceability of the pavement is expressed in terms of the Present Serviceability Index (PSI), and this is obtained from measurements of roughness and distress, e.g., cracking, patching, and rut depth (flexible) during the service life of the pavement and the traffic and climatic parameters are key to the measuring the Present Serviceability Index (PSI).

AASHTO Road Test was done using one subgrade soil that encountered swelling clay or frost heave, and the total change in PSI is obtained by summing the damaging effects of traffic, swelling clay, and frost heave. This method cannot adequately predict the performance in Liberia. The geotechnical properties of the subgrade soil are entirely different, and do not experience swelling nor frost heave.

2.1.2. Evaluation of traffic

Traffic is analyzed by converting a mixed traffic stream of different axle load and axle configuration into a design traffic number is to convert each expected axle load into an equivalent number of 18-kip single axle load and to sum these over the design period; this approach cannot accurately predict the traffic volume and traffic loading distribution. However, Traffic parameters are key to the performance of the pavement, with the growing increase in vehicle class distribution especially trucks with different axles (Tridem axles, Quadrem axles) (Mashayekhi et al., 2011).

2.1.3. Environment

Only one climatic condition was used for the AASHTO Road Test, the weather in Ottawa, Illinois was used for the AASHTO Road Test, subject to freezing temperatures during the winter and medium to high rainfall throughout the year and the procedure for estimating the effects of the seasonal condition of the pavement was based on experiment and field observation lasted for a limited period (2 years) not the entire pavement life. Pavement surface temperature goes below zero degrees in cold winters because of low air temperature and insufficient sunlight. Ice can be formed at pavement surfaces under specific weather conditions such as freezing rain and snowfall, making pavement surface slippery (Chen et al., 2019). The weather in Ottawa, Illinois, represents an average of seasonal effects in the United States.

On the contrary, the climate condition in Liberia differs. There is extensive rainfall and sunshine. With the AASHTO 1993 Guide for Design of Pavement Structure, it is not possible for the designers to input primary temperature data to predict the pavement performance.

2.1.4. Materials

Only one set of materials and one roadbed soil were included in the AASHTO Road Test for each pavement type. An experiment was done on the performance observations of stabilized base materials under asphalt surfaces. This experiment and the material property were used to characterize roadbed soil for pavement design using the resilient modulus (M_R) and subsequently prepare the pavement structure catalogue.

2.2. Pavement defects experience in Liberia due to inadequate design of pavement

Generally, it is observed that after the commissioning of newly constructed road or well-rehabilitated road which is very good in terms of the level of service, with the increase in the traffic volume and constantly changing weather, especially sunshine and huge rainfall the road quality deteriorates at every use of traffic mainly heavy vehicle. After some time, it gets completely deteriorated. Hence the level of service dropped down drastically as the road user increases, and maintenance is overlooked (*Pavement Failures*, n.d.).

Among many reasons associated with pavement failures, design fault is the primary reason why pavement fails prematurely and cannot provide the required level of service to the road users for or during the expected design life. Due to the poor design of pavement in Liberia, roads have many defects and when boiled down to the basics,

2.2.1. Fatigue (alligator) cracking

Figure 3. Fatigue (alligator) cracking ((Neal, 2017)

Fatigue (Alligator) Cracking is a load-associated structural failure. The failure occurs due to weakness in the surface, base, or subgrade; a surface or base is too thin; poor drainage, or the combination of all three. It often starts in the wheel path as longitudinal

cracking and results in fatigue cracking after severe distress (Neal, 2017).

2.2.2. Longitudinal (linear) cracking

Figure 4. Longitudinal (linear) cracking ((Neal, 2017)

Longitudinal cracks are long cracks that run parallel to the centerline of the roadway. These may be caused by joint failures, or they may be load-induced, and understanding the cause is critical to selecting the proper repair (*Pavement Failures*, n.d.).

2.2.3. Transverse Cracking

Figure 5. Transverse cracking (Dong et al., 2013)

Transverse cracks are single cracks perpendicular to the pavement's centerline or laydown direction. Transverse cracks can be caused by reflective cracks from an

underlying layer, daily temperature cycles, and poor construction due to improper operation of the paver (Neal, 2017).

2.2.4. Block cracking

Figure 6. Block cracking (Neal, 2017)

Block cracking is an interconnected series of cracks that divides the pavement into irregular pieces. This is sometimes the result of transverse and longitudinal cracks intersecting, and this is also due to lack of proper compaction during construction (*Pavement Failures*, n.d.).

2.2.5. Rutting

Figure 7. Rutting (Consortium, 2020)

Rutting is the displacement of pavement material that creates channels in the wheel path. Very severe rutting holds water in the rut. Rutting is usually a failure in one or more layers in the pavement (*Pavement Failures*, n.d.).

2.2.6. Shoving

Figure 8. Shoving (*Shoving (3) _ Pavement Interactive _ Flickr*, n.d.)

Shoving is the formation of ripples across a pavement. This characteristic shape is why this type of distress is sometimes called wash-boarding. Shoving occurs at locations having severe horizontal stresses, such as intersections. It is typically caused by excess asphalt, too much fine aggregate; rounded aggregate; or a weak granular base (Neal, 2017).

2.2.7. Potholes

Figure 9. Potholes (Neal, 2017)

Potholes are bowl-shaped holes similar to depressions. They are a progressive failure. First, small fragments of the top layer are dislodged. Over time, the distress goes down into the lower layers of the pavement. Potholes are often located in areas of poor

drainage areas; potholes are formed when the pavement disintegrates under traffic loading due to insufficient strength in one or more layers of the pavements, usually accompanied by water (Neal, 2017).

Conclusions

Pavement structure must defend the subgrade from excessive permanent deformation, resist loss of structural capacity from fatigue created by frequent traffic loads and provide good serviceability to users, without repair, for a given period. The pavement design engineer must provide the most cost-effective structure while optimizing the level of service provided to road users. However, the AASHTO 1993 Guide for Design of Pavement Structure is based on the AASHTO Road Test, which observed the performance of the pavement for two years, instead of the entire design life. It is only capable of forecasting performance within its development context. It lacks the ability to estimate long-term performance forecasting.

Given that this method has no consideration for materials properties except materials used for the AASHTO Road Test, it is essential to localize this design method by studying the design procedure and make the necessary adjustment to complement the environment, traffic, and materials. Similarly, many states in America and countries around the world have localized this design method due to the many limitations associated with AASHTO Road Test.

Recommendations

There is an urgent need for Liberia to develop its standard and guideline for road construction to be on a par with other countries in the region and Africa, mainly develop a Geometric Design Manual and Pavement Design Guideline and

subsequently develop a Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Structure Design Concept for Liberia. The Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Design Guide, also known as MEPDG, was released in 2004 by the National Cooperative Highway Research Program (NCHRP). It affords significant potential advantages over the AASHTO 1993 Guide for Design of Pavement Structure.

The Mechanistic-Empirical Pavement Design Guide presents a paradigm-shift in pavement design, allowed pavement design engineers to input parameters that affect pavement performance, comprising traffic, climate, pavement structure, materials properties, and combined with the practical principles of engineering mechanics to predict the pavement performance.

Finally, there is a need to organize a Road Infrastructure Management Systems (RIMS) to maintain and managed roads, and all physical assets within the road reserve, including but not limited to structures (Culverts, bridges, etc.). Key within the RIMS system should be the pavement management system with a well-organized database (using pavement management software like HDM III, HDM 4, Ronet) to stored pavement designed data, analyzed pavement condition, and present a thorough strategy for maintaining the condition of the road network pavement for a certain period at the lowest cost.

Disclaimer

The view conveyed in this paper and the precision of the facts confined in this is the sole responsibility of the author. It does not in any way represent the official view of his study universities (Vilnius Gediminas Technical University and Riga Technical University) neither of those who review this paper. This paper does not contain experimental data. Comments contained in

this paper are generated from research and the review of the previous document published on Liberia road network and the author personal observation and experience.

References

Agency, C. (2013). *Ministry of Public Works THE PREPARATORY SURVEY ON THE PROJECT FOR RECONSTRUCTION OF SOMALIA DRIVE IN MONLOVIA IN January 2013 KATAHIRA & ENGINEERS INTERNATIONAL. January.*

Austrroads. (2017). Guide to Pavement Technology Part 2: Pavement Structural Design. In *Austrroads Ltd.* (Vol. 66). www.austrroads.com.au

Board, H. R. (1962). The AASHO Road Test. *Special Report 61A - The History and Description of the Project.* <http://onlinepubs.trb.org/Onlinepubs/sr/sr61g/61g.pdf>

Chapter 1 - NHI-05-037 - Geotech - Bridges & Structures - Federal Highway Administration. (n.d.).

Chen, J., Wang, H., & Xie, P. (2019). Pavement temperature prediction: Theoretical models and critical affecting factors. In *Applied Thermal Engineering* (Vol. 158). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2019.113755>

Consortium, P. T. (2020). *Rutting - Pavement Interactive.* <https://pavementinteractive.org/reference-desk/pavement-management/pavement-distresses/rutting/>

Dong, Q., Jiang, X., Huang, B., & Richards, S. H. (2013). Analyzing influence factors of transverse cracking on LTPP resurfaced asphalt pavements through NB and ZINB models. *Journal of Transportation Engineering*, 139(9), 889–895.

[https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)TE.1943-5436.0000568](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)TE.1943-5436.0000568)

Li, Q., Xiao, D. X., Wang, K. C. P., Hall, K. D., & Qiu, Y. (2011). Mechanistic-empirical pavement design guide (MEPDG): a bird's-eye view. *Journal of Modern Transportation*, 19(2), 114–133.

<https://doi.org/10.1007/bf03325749>

Mashayekhi, M., Amini, A. A., Behbahani, H., & Nobakht, S. (2011). Comparison of Mechanistic-Empirical and Empirical Flexible Pavement Design Procedures of Aashto : a Case Study. *5th INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE BITUMINOUS MIXTURES AND PAVEMENTS, June*, 319–328.

Neal, B. (2017). *13 Pavement Defects and Failures You Should Know! | Paveman Pro* (p. 1).

http://www.pavemanpro.com/article/identifying_asphalt_pavement_defects/

O'Flaherty, C. A. (2020). Introduction to pavement design. In *Highways* (pp. 241–282).

<https://doi.org/10.1201/9781482269291-17>

Transportation Officials. (1993). *AASHTO Guide for Design of Pavement Structures, 1993* (Vol. 1). Aashto.